

Liquid-Liquid Extraction of Cadmium(II) and Lead(II) as their Ethyl Xanthates

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Methods of quantitative extraction of cadmium and lead with potassium ethylxanthate into carbon tetrachloride, the effect of sixteen cations and ten anions on these extraction, their separation from the interfering ions in binary, ternary and quaternary mixtures as well as estimation (EDTA) after stripping are described. Applicability of the methods are established through analysis of Zn and Pb in standard ores, alloys and scrap material.

The literature records on the aspects of extraction behaviour and analytical application of the metal alkylxanthates¹⁻⁴, $[M^{n+}(R-O-CS_2)_m]^{n-m}$, hint a need for more detailed studies. Such studies with zinc xanthate has been considered earlier⁵. The present paper describes the conditions for extraction of ethylxanthate complexes of lead and cadmium, the effect of diverse ions, stripping of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} from the organic extracts, their separation from the interfering ions and possible use of the extraction systems in counter-current process. Also described is this extractive method for somewhat quick but quantitative separation and subsequent estimation (EDTA) of lead and zinc in some alloys ores, and zinc in a zinc scrap.

Results and Discussion

The results are discussed on the basis of single extractions with carbon tetrachloride (1:1 phase volume ratio) unless otherwise mentioned.

The stable Cd-xanthate complex (1:2)⁶ is completely extracted (>98%) at pH 4-11 when the mole ratio of Cd:Xn is approximately 1:4. Complete extraction of the Pb-xanthate complex (1:2)⁶ however, takes place at pH~2.5 and again at pH 5-8, mole ratio of Pb:Xn being 1:3.5. The results of the variation of percentage extraction with pH, for both, are shown in Fig. 1. In the case of lead the curve passes through a minimum at pH~4 (KAc/HAc 0.34 N/1.5 N). This phenomenon may be attributed to a decrease in the reaction rate due to non-equilibrium extraction⁷. It is observed that (i) increase in shaking time at this pH from 3 to 60 min, improves correspondingly the extraction, 48.8 to 100%, (ii) a change of the sequence of addition of the reagents, i.e. from buffer and xanthate to xanthate and buffer, betters the extraction by 7 to 8% for each constant period of shaking, and (iii) a change of the extractant, from carbon tetrachloride to benzene[†] augments the extraction (48.8 to 100%) in 3 min shaking. The

same behaviour is observed at pH 3.25; here also the extraction limit is improved with the time of shaking (viz 60, 85 and 100% respectively, with 3, 15 and 30 min). The addition of a few drops of pyridine to the system has been found to enhance the extraction and helps to form clear separation of the phases.

It is interesting to note that a solution of xanthic acid in carbon tetrachloride (XnH-CCl₄)[‡] extracts more than 98% of lead from the aqueous solutions of moderately concentrated HNO₃ (1.5 N) to pH~10 (NH₄Cl/NH₄OH). Similar to the study with the Zn-xanthate system⁸, an iterative use of the CCl₄ extract, having been stripped of cadmium or lead with HNO₃, has been found possible. This offers an economy in the use of xanthate and a potential application as well in counter-current extraction and recycling systems.

The effect of various ions on a single extraction of cadmium and lead under the conditions of general procedure was examined. Alkali and alkaline earth metals do not interfere. It is seen that Zn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Hg^{II}, Bi^{III}, As^{III}, Sb^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, UO₂^{II} and EDTA²⁻ always interfere in both the systems. Besides, Pb^{II} interferes in the Cd-xanthate system, and Cd^{II}, HF₂⁻, H₂PO₄⁻, S₂O₃²⁻ and CrO₄²⁻ interfere in the Pb-xanthate system. Depending upon the nature of interference, methods of quantitative separation (>98%) of cadmium and lead from binary mixtures have been adapted and accomplished⁸.

[†]Benzene also extracts the Pb-xanthate complex.

[‡]XnH-CCl₄ may be prepared by adding slowly 3-4 drops of concentrated HCl to an immiscible system of equal volume (15 ml) of aqueous solution of 2% K-ethylxanthate and CCl₄ while shaking continuously, and separating the organic layer. The Xn⁻ ion concentration (iodimetry) in the initial aqueous solution and in the organic phase after extraction are 14.9 and 3.9 mg ml⁻¹ respectively.

Fig. 1. (Δ , Δ' , Δ) Extraction time 3 min (\sim 2 strokes/s). Sequence of reagent addition—first buffer then xanthate. Extraction time for Pb-xanthate complex: (1●) 15, (2●) 30, (3●) 45 and (4●) 60 min.

Quantitative separation of Zn, Cd and Pb in ternary mixtures and Zn, Cd, Pb and Hg in a quarternary mixture : For quantitative separation of the ions in ternary and quarternary mixtures the methods, viz. (i) use of K-Et-xanthate together with an extraction (CCl_4) and stripping (a and b), and (ii) CCl_4 solution of xanthic acid $\text{XnH}-\text{CCl}_4$ (c) have been tested. The results are shown in Table 1. The second method (c) has been found to work well with the quarternary mixture. (a) The mixture is adjusted to $\text{pH}\sim 10$ ($\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}/\text{NH}_4\text{OH}$), treated with Xn^- solution (3% ; 7 ml), extracted with CCl_4 (+ 2 drops of pyridine). Zn retains in the aqueous phase and estimated with EDTA. Cd and Pb together are stripped from

the organic phase (two portions of 0.5N HNO_3) and they are titrated with EDTA (Cd+Pb). The EDTA bound to Cd is then made free (1,10-phenanthroline)⁹ and titrated against a standard $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution. (b) The three ions together are extracted as xanthate into CCl_4 (+ 2–3 drops of pyridine) at $\text{pH}\sim 6$ (KAc/HAc). Zn is stripped with an ammoniacal buffer⁵ of $\text{pH}\sim 8$. Cd and Pb in the organic phase are estimated as in (a), or by stripping them separately, first Cd with 0.1N HCl plus a few drops of xanthate solution (2%), then Pb with HNO_3 (0.5 N). (c) The acidified mixture (0.8–1.0 N HNO_3) is extracted with $\text{XnH}-\text{CCl}_4$ containing 2–3 drops of pyridine solution when only Pb is extracted. It

TABLE 1—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Pb^{II} AND Hg^{II} FROM TERNARY AND QUARTENARY MIXTURES

Ternary mixtures :											
Ions	Quantity (mg) in synthetic mixtures				Quantity (mg) recovered (std. deviation) using procedures						
	(i)	(ii)	(iii)	(iv)	(a) for (i)	(b) for (ii)	(c) for				
							(iii)	(iv)*			
Zn^{II}	2.85	1.71	5.70	1.71	2.86 (0.08)	1.73 (0.01)	5.59 (0.03)	1.73			
Cd^{II}	5.18	2.59	5.18	2.59	5.19 (0.01)	2.65 (0.04)	4.93 (0.04)	2.64			
Pb^{II}	8.83	4.41	2.21	4.41	8.40 (0.11)	4.34 (0.05)	2.23 (0.13)	4.36			
*The ternary mixture has been analysed once.											
Quarternary mixture :											
Quantity (mg) in synthetic mixtures				Zn^{II}		Cd^{II}		Pb^{II}		Hg^{II}	
Quantity recovered (std. deviations)				2.84		5.28		2.28		5.0	
				2.83 (0.02)		5.25 (0.04)		2.28 (0.01)		retained in org. phase	

is stripped (HNO₃, 0.5–1.0 *N*) and estimated. The acidity of the aqueous phase is then reduced (KOH) and Zn and Cd are separated following the earlier method⁸.

Extractive separation and estimation of zinc and lead in alloys and ores: The present extractive method of separation of the metal xanthate complexes has been utilised in the determination of zinc in two manganese bronze alloys (10e, 10f), in a commercial zinc scrap, and lead and zinc in two ores (a lead-ore 42 dg and a zinc-ore 41 cg). The samples were digested with HNO₃ (1 : 1), evaporated almost to dryness, treated with water, filtered and made up to 50 ml (100 ml for zinc scrap solution). Aliquots from each such stock solutions (5 ml from Zn-ore and 1 ml from others) were analysed for lead and zinc through extraction, stripping and estimation (EDTA). The experimental conditions, the average result of more than of three analyses in each case with the corresponding standard deviations, and the standard results of the samples are shown in Table 2. Since no reliable data for zinc content in the commercial zinc scrap was available, for comparison, it was determined with a standard potassium ferrocyanide solution⁹.

Experimental

In general, a 1% aqueous solution of potassium ethylxanthate (99% ; Fluka) was used. All other chemicals were of C.P. or A.R. grade. The water used was always demineralised and distilled. The pH values of the aqueous solutions, before and after extraction, were determined with narrow range pH paper (E. Merck) and also with a pH meter (Labor pH meter, Knick, and Ingold Electroden, Germany). In order to study the extraction behaviour with the pH of the aqueous solutions, the latter were maintained with buffers : for Cd-xanthate, 2 ≤ pH ≤ 3.5-CICH₂COOH/CICH₂COOK, 4.5 ≤ pH ≤ 7.5-CH₃COOH/CH₃COOK and 8 ≤ pH ≤ 11-NH₄OH/NH₄Cl ; and for Pb-xanthate, 1 ≤ pH ≤ 2 glycine/HCl, ~7-CH₃COONH₄ and 8 ≤ pH ≤ 12 glycine/KOH. Alloys and ores were purchased from Bureau of Analysed Samples Ltd. (U.K.) and zinc scraps collected from local market at Calcutta.

General procedure : Cd: The water-insoluble white Cd-xanthate formed from Cd(NO₃)₂ (0.046 *M* ; 0.9 ml), KCl (2 *N* ; 1 ml), CH₃COOH (2 *N*, 2 ml), water (10–11 ml) and Xn⁻ (5 ml), was extracted in a separatory funnel into carbon tetrachloride or chloroform (20 ml+2 drops pyridine, 2 strokes/s for 1 min). The aqueous layer after

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF ZINC AND LEAD IN ALLOYS AND ORES

Alloy/Ore analysed amount (g)	Buffer/Acid used before extraction	Amount (ml) of 2% aq. Xn ⁻ used	Vol. CCl ₄ for extracn. (ml)	CCl ₄ -XnH soln. used (ml)	1st stripping soln. used	Zn found %	2nd strppng soln. used	Pb found %	Standrd deviation		Standard value (%)	
									Zn	Pb	Zn	Pb
Manganese bronze 10e (0.3227)	10 ml KAc/HAc pH~6	10	20+5, 20+5 ^a	—	25 ml 0.1 <i>N</i> HCl	31.54	—	—	0.25	—	31.5	—
Manganese bronze 10f (0.2643)	10 ml KAc/HAc pH~6	10	20+5, 20+5 ^a	—	25 ml 0.1 <i>N</i> HCl	35.66	—	—	0.33	—	35.8	—
Pb-conc. ore 42g (0.2917)	10 ml NaAc/HAc pH~6	5	20+5, 3 drops pyridine	—	25+25 ml NH ₃ /NH ₄ Cl pH~8	17.58	25 ml 0.5 <i>N</i> HNO ₃	59.22	0.35	0.25	17.1	59.5
, ,	10 ml HNO ₃ 0.75 <i>N</i> , 4 ml water	—	—	15 ml ^b , 3 drops pyridine	15+15 ml 1 <i>N</i> HNO ₃ for Pb	17.58	—	59.22	0.35	0.25	17.1	59.5
Zn-conc. ore 41cg (1.079)	7 ml HNO ₃ 1.5 <i>N</i> , 5 ml water	—	—	17+5 ml ^b , 3 drops pyridine	30 ml 1 <i>N</i> HNO ₃ for Pb	48.50 ^c	—	0.705 ^d	0.30	0.006	59.5	0.71
Zn-scrap commercial (0.5116)	10 ml HNO ₃ 0.1 <i>N</i> , 4 ml water	—	—	15+5 ml ^b , 1 drop pyridine	—	54.45	—	—	—	—	54.2 ^e	—
, ,	10 ml KAc/HAc pH~6	7	20+5, 1 drop pyridine	—	25+25 ml NH ₃ /NH ₄ Cl pH~8	54.45	—	—	—	—	54.2 ^e	—

^a2nd. time extraction was carried out with the organic extract that had been stripped of zinc with 0.1*N* HCl. A single operation extracts more than 94% of zinc.

^b3.89 mg Xn⁻/ml of the solution. After extraction the organic layer was shaken with its equal volume of 0.005–0.01*N* KOH to remove any xanthic acid in it.

^cThe aq. phase (after treatment of 5 ml of the stock solution with the organic extractant) was made up to 100 ml with water and out of that 10 ml was used for Zn estimation.

^dEDTA of 0.0050*M* was used for lead in the organic extract from a 5 ml stock solution.

^eZi^c in the stock solution was estimated by [Fe(CN)₆]⁴⁻-Na-diphenylamine sulphonate method.

Xn⁻ = K-ethylxanthate, CCl₄-XnH = solution of xanthic acid in CCl₄ (q.v. 3rd method of separation of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ in a mixture of the three).

being separated was extracted with a further amount of the organic solvent (5 ml). The cadmium in the combined extract was re-extracted into an equal volume of 0.3 *N* HNO₃ (stripping solution) with shaking for 2–3 min and was estimated complexometrically (EDTA, hexamine, xylenol orange).

Pb: The procedure with the insoluble yellow-white Pb-xanthate system including extractant, stripping solution and subsequent estimation of lead was the same as Cd xanthate. The only difference in the use of the chemicals are: Pb (NO₃)₂ 0.107 *M*, buffer of pH 5.5–6.0 CH₃COOH/CH₃COOK (6 ml), Xn⁻ (3 ml), CCl₄ (15 ml+2 drops pyridine), shaking time 2 min, further CCl₄ (5 ml), and stripping solution 0.5 *N* HNO₃.

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